

Software generation of local extremes tasks of equal difficulty

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Abstract

In this paper, we discuss the possibilities of software generation of mathematical tasks of equal difficulty for the local extrema of polynomial and rational functions of one variable and polynomial functions of two variables. The software we used for this purpose is Moodle with the STACK extension and Maxima.

Introduction

With the development of new and advanced technologies, new possibilities for their use in teaching are emerging. One such possibility is software generation of mathematical problems corresponding to the required area, difficulty, and other input parameters. This allows teachers to create a large number of exercises for practicing the subject matter while maintaining the desired properties of the problems. This has the potential to streamline the teaching process and improve students' understanding of mathematical problems.

Many studies have focused on the integration of ICT into mathematics education. It has been shown that the proper use of ICT in the teaching process improves mathematics education and helps students understand key concepts (Aggarwal, Gupta, 2020). Other research indicates that the use of ICT in teaching contributes to student engagement in the educational process (active learning), supports self-directed learning, and enables students to work remotely (Asare, 2023; Das, 2019).

In this paper, we focus on the software generation of tasks to investigate local extrema of polynomial and rational functions of one real variable and polynomial functions of two variables, with the requirement that stationary points have integer or rational coordinates if calculated from a linear equation, and integer coordinates if calculated from a quadratic equation. We use Moodle with the STACK plugin (utilizing Maxima for STACK) as a tool, but the considerations described are generally applicable.

When creating sets of tasks of the same type, a teacher sometimes wants the results to be from given numerical sets. To generate problems of the same difficulty, the simplest and most natural choice for students is when integer solutions are produced. This is not always necessary, but in structurally more complex problems, it is a simplifying factor. Essentially, it is about being able to separate different types of results when generating them so that they are either specifically included or excluded.

Polynomial functions of one variable

For our purposes, we consider quadratic and cubic polynomials. If a student knows how to find integer roots of polynomials of the third and higher degrees, the procedure described for the cubic polynomial can naturally be extended. The task of the prepared exercises is to find stationary points (we will not deal with investigating the existence and type of extrema here). Recall that stationary points are found as the solution to the equation where the derivative of the function is set to zero.

First, consider the quadratic function $f(x) = ax^2 + bx + c$. Setting the derivative to zero gives the linear equation $2ax + b = 0$, the solution of which, for integer a, b, c is rational and equal to $x = \frac{-b}{2a}$. In this case, any integer coefficients a, b, c can be generated, with the only condition being that a is non-zero.

In the case of a cubic function, the stationary points will be the solutions of a quadratic equation. Depending on the control of the generation, we may want to allow integer solutions, rational solutions, or solutions with square roots in the real domain. Rational and irrational solutions can be achieved by controlling through the discriminant (which could also be elaborated), but we will limit ourselves to integer solutions and show the way to generate them from the back. Thus, we will not generate directly the coefficients of the optimized cubic function, but instead generate the integer stationary points, i.e., directly the solutions of the quadratic equation. The function for the problem statement is then obtained by integrating the intended quadratic function.

We assume $f'(x) = k(x - a)(x - b) = k(x^2 - (a + b)x + ab)$, where a and b are generated integer roots and k is a constant specified below. Thus, $f(x)$ is the primitive function: $f(x) = k(\frac{1}{3}x^3 - \frac{a+b}{2}x^2 + abx) + c$. If we want the problem statement to also have integer coefficients, we choose k as any multiple of six. Another option is to take k as a multiple of three and ensure that $a + b$ is even within some additional condition. Note that the coefficient c can be taken arbitrarily.

Rational function of one variable

Task of finding stationary points, namely points suspected of being extremes. Again, we approach this from the end. The situation is more complex with many more scenarios. We expect the derivative of the function in the form

$$f'(x) = \frac{P(x)}{Q(x)}.$$

The solution of the equation $P(x) = 0$ may require factoring out up to x^2 and solving a linear or quadratic equation. The function $f(x)$ is obtained again by integration, but this time the antiderivative may include not only the intended rational function but also logarithmic and arctangent functions. It is necessary to handle the conditions so that the function specified is exclusively rational, with coefficients of other functions needing to be zero. We will analyse possible variants, specifically describing the solutions of three of them, while for the others we will only state the conditions found.

In further considerations, we assume that the function $P(x)$ is in one of the following forms: $P_{1+k} = x^k(x - a)$, $P_{4+k} = x^k(x - a)(x - b)$, $P_{7+k} = x^k(x^2 + c)$ where $k \in \{0,1,2\}$, a and b are integers (non-zero), and c is positive. We expect the function $Q(x)$ to be in one of the four forms: $Q_1 = [x - m]^2$, $Q_2 = [x^2 - m^2]^2$, $Q_3 = [x^2 + n]^2$, $Q_4 = [x - m]^3$, where m is an integer and n is positive. These combinations yield the most common rational functions used to solve stationary point problems of this type.

Further, let's denote

$$f'_{ij} = \frac{P_i}{Q_j}.$$

For example

$$f'_{11} = \frac{x - a}{[x - m]^2}.$$

This derivative has a single zero point at $x = a$. However, the primitive function of f'_{11}

$$f_{11} = \log(x - m) - \frac{m - a}{x - m}$$

is never rational, therefore it cannot be used for our purposes. Next, the function

$$f'_{21} = \frac{x(x - a)}{[x - m]^2}$$

has two zero points $x = a$ and $x = 0$. The primitive function of f'_{21} is

$$f_{21} = (2m - a) \log(x - m) + \frac{x^2 - mx - m^2 + am}{x - m}$$

and it is rational only under the condition $a = 2m$. So only integer m can be generated.

For the third time,

$$f'_{43} = \frac{(x - a)(x - b)}{[x^2 + n]^2}$$

has two zero points at $x = a$ and $x = b$ and the primitive function

$$f_{43} = \frac{(n + ab) \operatorname{atan}\left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{n}}\right)}{2n^{\frac{3}{2}}} - \frac{(n - ab)x + (-b - a)n}{2nx^2 + 2n^2}.$$

This is rational under the condition $n + ab = 0$. During generation, we generate two parameters (taking into account that $n > 0$) and calculate the third one.

We attach the results of the conditions for different combinations of numerators P_i and denominators Q_j of derivatives f'_{ij} . Note that in STACK or Maxima, the function f_{ij} can be found using the command $f_{ij}; \operatorname{integrate}(f'_{ij}, x);$

$f'_{11}: \emptyset$	$f'_{12}: a = 0$	$f'_{13}: a = 0$	$f'_{14}: \text{without conditions}$
$f'_{21}: a - 2m = 0$	$f'_{22}: \emptyset$	$f'_{23}: \emptyset$	$f'_{24}: \emptyset$
$f'_{31}: 3m^2 - 2am = 0$	$f'_{32}: 2m - b - a = 0$	$f'_{33}: \emptyset$	$f'_{34}: 3m - a = 0$
$f'_{41}: 2m = b + a$	$f'_{42}: m^2 - ab = 0$	$f'_{43}: n + ab = 0$	$f'_{44}: \text{without conditions}$
$f'_{51}: 3m^2 - 2(a + b)m + ab = 0$	$f'_{52}: m = 0, a + b = 0$	$f'_{53}: \emptyset$	$f'_{54}: 3m - b - a = 0$
$f'_{61}: 4m^3 - 3(a + b)m^2 + 2abm = 0$	$f'_{62}: 3m^2 + 2(a + b)m + ab = 0$	$f'_{63}: ab - 3n = 0, a + b = 0$	$f'_{64}: 6m^2 - 3(a + b)m + ab = 0$
$f'_{71}: m = 0$	$f'_{72}: m^2 = c$	$f'_{73}: n + c = 0$	$f'_{74}: \emptyset$
$f'_{81}: \emptyset$	$f'_{82}: \emptyset$	$f'_{83}: \emptyset$	$f'_{84}: m = 0$
$f'_{91}: 4m^3 + 2cm = 0$	$f'_{92}: \emptyset$	$f'_{93}: c - 3n = 0$	$f'_{94}: \emptyset$

Table 1: Conditions for generating rational functions

Polynomial function of two variables

In the theory of functions of two real variables, the situation is more complicated already with polynomial functions. Stationary points are sought here as a solution to the system of equations that arise by putting partial derivatives equal to zero. Stationary points now have two coordinates that satisfy a system of two equations for two unknowns. The simplest situation is in the case of a linear system of equations. Considering the difficulty of the calculation, this time we can let the rational coordinates of the stationary points come out. In the case of a non-linear system, however, we will want the coordinates to be integers.

Again, we will approach the preparation of the tasks from behind - we will directly generate the coordinates of the stationary points, which will be the solutions of the specified types of systems. For a system of equations to arise from the partial derivatives of a function of two variables $f(x, y)$, the condition of equality for mixed derivatives of the second order must hold: $f''_{xy} = f''_{yx}$.

We denote the partial derivatives of the first order $f'_x(x, y) = P(x, y)$ and $f'_y(x, y) = Q(x, y)$. Then function $f(x, y)$ is found as the so-called stem function to $P(x, y)$ and $Q(x, y)$ by solving an exact differential equation

$$P(x, y) dx + Q(x, y) dy = 0.$$

Note that in Maxima or STACK we can use the command $\text{ode2}(\text{'diff}(y,x) = - P(x,y)/Q(x,y), y, x)$; to solve the exact differential equation.

In the task design, we will focus on the following two groups. First, the stationary point will be one, calculated as a solution to a linear system of equations for two unknowns. Then one of the partial derivatives will have two real roots in one variable. In each such group, multiple options will need to be considered, since the described conditions can be applied to both x and y partial derivatives.

- $f'_x = ax + b, f'_y = cy + d$

The mixed partial derivative is zero in both cases. Therefore, it is sufficient to generate numbers a, b, c, d, K integer, a, c non-zero. The stem function then has the form

$$f(x, y) = cy^2 + 2dy + ax^2 + 2bx + K .$$

And the stationary point has coordinates $\left[\frac{-b}{a}, \frac{-d}{c}\right]$.

- $f'_x = cy + d, f'_y = ax + b$

Mixed partial derivative are $f''_{xy} = c, f''_{yx} = a$. From there we have the condition $a = c$. Therefore, it is sufficient to generate numbers a, b, d, K integer, a non-zero. The stem function then has the form

$$f(x, y) = axy + by + dx + K .$$

A stationary point has coordinates $\left[\frac{-d}{a}, \frac{-b}{a}\right]$.

- $f'_x = (x - a)(x - b), f'_y = cy + d$

The mixed partial derivative is zero in both cases. It is enough to generate numbers a, b, c, d, K integer, c non-zero. The stem function is then of the form

$$f(x, y) = 3cy^2 + 6dy + 2x^3 + (-(3b) - 3a)x^2 + 6abx + K .$$

There are two stationary points: $\left[a, \frac{-d}{c}\right], \left[b, \frac{-d}{c}\right]$.

- $f'_x = (x - a)(x - b), f'_y = (y - c)(y - d)$

The mixed partial derivative is zero in both cases. It is enough to generate numbers a, b, c, d, K integer. The stem function is then of the form

$$f(x, y) = 2y^3 + (-(3d) - 3c)y^2 + 6cdy + 2x^3 + (-(3b) - 3a)x^2 + 6abx + K .$$

There are four stationary points: $[a, c], [b, c], [a, d], [b, d]$.

- $f'_x = 2xy - (a + b)y + c, f'_y = (x - a)(x - b)$

The mixed partial derivatives are equal $2y - (a + b)$. It is enough to generate numbers a, b, c, K integer such that $a \neq b$. The stem function is then of the form

$$f(x, y) = x^2y - (a + b)xy + aby + cx + K .$$

There are two stationary points: $\left[a, \frac{-c}{a-b}\right], \left[b, \frac{-c}{b-a}\right]$. Note that instead of c in the partial derivative with respect to x , the function $c(x)$ of the variable x could be, but the calculation of the y coordinate would still be from a linear equation.

Other variants of the previous types can be obtained by directly exchanging the variables x and y in the partial derivatives from which the problems are developed. The situations would be analogous, so we will not list them.

Conclusion

The paper presents the possibility of software generation of mathematical tasks of the same difficulty, which is demonstrated in a specific area. We chose the local extremes of one real variable and two real variables, while as a software solution we used Moodle with the STACK extension (including Maxima support).

Educators can use such a pre-prepared environment in mathematics courses and thus make the education process more efficient. By extending it to several mathematical areas and problems, it is possible to create a course that can be used for students' home preparation, test preparation, or directly in the classroom. Within one mathematical area, it is possible to generate tasks of varying difficulty, allowing students to practice their skills on a large number of tasks.

The software we chose is capable of working with mathematical text, randomly generating tasks according to a pre-programmed form, evaluating the correctness of solving individual tasks, evaluating the equivalence of expressions (whether the student's answer is equivalent to the correct answer) and more. All this has the potential to improve and make the educational process more efficient, but a disadvantage is the rather demanding preparation required in this software environment.

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STACK: <https://stack-assessment.org/>

Maxima for STACK: <https://docs.stack-assessment.org/en/CAS/Maxima/>